

Key results of our previous study (Navakeatpreecha et al., 2024)

- The fresh mulberry leaf treatment was the condition the moth preferred for egg laying.
- The expression levels of four *BmOr* genes, *BmOr44*, *BmOr54*, *BmOr56*, and *BmOr63*, in almost all conditions, except fresh mulberry leaves, were higher than those of the control.
- This result implied that these four genes might play an important role in egg laying.

Disruption of their expression levels might affect the oviposition rate of moths.